

EMPLOYING ANN AND MLR TO PREDICT FLEXURAL STRENGTH OF CORN COB REINFORCED LOW-DENSITY POLYETHYLENE WASTE COMPOSITES

Agha Inya NDUKWE^{1*}, Paulinus IFEDINIRU¹, Wasiu Oyeyemi SALAMI², Bobmanuel Chigozie IWUANYANWU¹, Precious C. ALLWELL¹, Chigozie Ignatius ONYECHERE³, Oluebube Perpetua EZIKE¹, Benedict OJIAKU¹, Izuchukwu Somto ODUARO¹, Ikechukwu J. OJUKWU¹

¹Department of Materials & Metallurgical Engineering, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.

²Department of Polymer Technology, Nigerian Institute of Leather and Science Technology, Zaria

³Department of Civil Engineering, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.

Corresponding author, Agha Inya Ndukwe, email: agha.ndukwe@futo.edu.ng

(ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1723-7026>)

ABSTRACT: The growing problem of plastic waste worldwide calls for creative methods of material recycling and the production of sustainable composites. The mechanical improvement of low-density polyethylene waste (LDPEw) using maize cob agricultural waste reinforcement is examined in this work, which addresses waste valorization and sustainable material development. The use of FTIR spectroscopy, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), and differential thermal analysis (DTA) to characterize maize cob filler verified its thermal stability up to 250°C and the existence of functional groups linked to lignin that are necessary for interactions between polymers and fibers. Standardized testing procedures were used to systematically assess the mechanical characteristics of the composites, which were produced via compression molding with corn cob loadings ranging from 0 to 10%. The results of statistical analysis showed that the ideal filler loadings rely on the properties: the greatest impact strength was attained at 2 weight percent (0.4343 ± 0.02 J/mm), the maximum flexural strength was at 4 weight percent (35.94 ± 0.8 MPa), and the maximum hardness peaked at 8 weight percent (53.13 ± 1.2 HV). At 10 weight percent loading, tensile strength showed a notable recovery pattern, first dropping by 51% and then surpassing baseline matrix strength by 21.2% (61.74 ± 1.5 MPa). Artificial neural networks (ANN) and multiple linear regression (MLR) were used in predictive modeling. The results showed that MLR was more accurate than ANN in predicting flexural strength (Mean Absolute Error (MAE) = -0.000167 vs 0.005333).

KEYWORDS: Corn Cob, Composite, Low-Density Polyethylene Waste (LDPEw), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Multiple Linear Regression (MLR)

1 INTRODUCTION

Waste in all areas of the land and water has dramatically increased as a result of the 300 million tons of manufactured plastics produced worldwide in 2013. Each of the seven billion people on the earth currently consumes about 40 kg of plastic annually. Because plastic is sturdy, flexible, lightweight, moisture-resistant, and reasonably priced, it has several benefits over older materials like glass, wood, leather, and metals. Due to the widespread use of single-use plastic food packaging and the throw-away mindset, the amount of plastic garbage in cities, beaches, and waterways has significantly risen in recent decades. According to studies, 40% of plastic trash ends up in landfills, 14% gets recycled, and

32% ends up as litter in the ocean (Fayshal et al., 2023).

With a 62% market share, synthetic fibers currently lead the worldwide fiber business, while natural fibers account for 38%. In addition to using more energy during manufacturing, synthetic fibers also add to environmental problems. This is because dangerous substances including sulfuric acid and mixed petroleum compounds were released (Wong et al., 2024). Researchers have lately become interested in natural fibers because of their availability, affordability, sustainability, renewable nature, and biodegradability. They may also be utilized as reinforcement in polymer composites (Mishra et al., 2022).

Corn cob has been shown to be a viable reinforcing agent in polymer matrices in earlier studies. The mechanical characterization of the treated husk composites showed superior tensile strength, flexural strength, and hardness compared to the untreated ones and pure LDPE, according to Alichó et al.'s (2024) study on the effect of surface treatments on Zea mays husk and the behavior of husk/Low-Density Polyethylene Composites. The treatment improved the composites' crystallinity and reduced their propensity to absorb water, but it had no effect on their thermal stability. It was determined that using treated Z. mays husk as a reinforcing ingredient might improve the overall performance of green composites while also making them more affordable and sustainable. Additional research has been conducted to compare the performance of corn fiber plastic composites made from various parts of the corn stalk. The results showed that the highest flexural strength (46.10 MPa) and tensile break strength (26.58 MPa) were obtained when the corn stem, which has the highest cellulose content, was used as reinforcement. However, the content of hemicellulose should be lower, as this was correlated with the water resistance. The leaf-reinforced corn fiber plastic composite (CFPC) showed the lowest performance due to the high hemicellulose content in the corn leaf, with a flexural strength of 28.70 MPa

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Characterization of corn cob

2.1.1 FTIR test

Agilent Technologies to analyze a sample of a corn cob. The goal was to investigate the existence of functional groups in the corn cob, which can provide important details about its chemical makeup. To prepare the corn cob sample for examination, it was ground into a fine powder. The FTIR spectrometer from Agilent Technologies that was used for the analysis had a Happ-Genzel apodization feature. To account for any influence from the surroundings, 16 background scans were acquired in addition to the 30 sample scans. The spectral range was adjusted at 4000 to 650 cm^{-1} and the resolution was 8.

2.1.2 TGA test

To learn more about the thermal behavior of the maize cob sample in this experiment, TGA was carried out using a PerkinElmer Analyzer. A sample of a maize cob was obtained, weighing 18.302 mg and having a particle size of 250 microns. The PerkinElmer Analyzer's crucible was filled with the sample maize cob. The TGA study was carried out using a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, commencing at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and finishing at 950 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Throughout the heating

and a tensile break strength of 15.98 MPa. When combined, the results indicated that the stem or cob was the more appropriate corn fiber for the preparation of CFPC (Luo et al., 2017).

Predicting and optimizing properties has been transformed by the use of artificial intelligence into materials science. Multiple linear regression (MLR) and artificial neural networks (ANN) have demonstrated promise in predicting the mechanical characteristics of biocomposites; however, there are few comparative studies assessing their efficacy for corn cob-LDPE systems. Comprehensive optimization of corn cob-LDPE composites taking into account several mechanical parameters at once is yet unknown, despite encouraging initial results. Furthermore, there is a paucity of systematic research on the relative efficacy of ANN versus MLR for property prediction in these systems.

The objectives of this research are to: (1) characterize corn cob filler for use in composite applications; (2) study how corn cob loading (0–10 weight percent) affects the mechanical characteristics of LDPE waste composites; (3) establish and assess ANN and MLR models for predicting flexural strength; and (4) determine interactions between processing, structure, and properties for the best possible composite design.

A popular method for analyzing both organic and inorganic materials is Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. In this experiment, we used an FTIR spectrometer from procedure, the sample weight was continuously measured and recorded.

2.1.3 DTA test

The essence of the DTA test on the corn cob was to ascertain the temperatures associated with the sample's thermal phenomena, such as phase changes and breakdown. The sample of maize cob utilized for the test had a particle size of 250 microns and weighed 18.302 mg. The sample was heated under controlled conditions at a rate of 10.00 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ from a starting temperature of 30.00 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to a final temperature of 950.00 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the DTA analysis on a PerkinElmer Analyzer.

2.1.4 SEM of composites

The tested composites were subjected to electron microscopic examination in accordance with ASTM E986 specifications using the Pro: X: Phenom world 800-07334 model. A 0.5g portion of the sample was painstakingly prepared and attached to the sample holder. The chamber was then tightly sealed, and the sample holder was carefully positioned beneath the machine's magnification screen. After observing the sample's microscopic properties, a particular region

of interest was further enlarged at various degrees of electron microscopy to produce a clear visualization, which was then recorded in accordance with protocol.

2.2 Production of the composite

2.2.1 Mixing

The composite samples were created by using a mixing technique while the two wheels of the mill machine were rotating counterclockwise. The material began to soften because of this process, which took place in a matter of 5 minutes at a constant temperature of 170 °C. The fiber was gradually added to the bank, well mixed, and given 3 minutes to integrate with the matrix after the polymer had formed a band and bank on the front roll. Furthermore, the final composite was sheeted and tagged for identification.

2.2.2 Hot pressing

After the mixing procedure was finished, the resultant composite was carefully placed into a metal mold that was 120 mm x 100 mm x 3.2 mm in size. The composite assembly was then moved to a hydraulic hot press, more particularly a Compression Moulding Machine, where it underwent shaping under carefully regulated circumstances for 5 minutes at 150 °C temperature and 2.5 MPa pressure. The composite was properly cooled after the allotted amount of time, removed from the mould, and labeled.

2.3 Mechanical tests

2.3.1 Impact test

The impact test was carried out precisely in accordance with the ASTM D-156 standard. Each specimen from all the created blend samples was painstakingly prepared by being cut to measurements of 64 mm x 12.7 mm x 3.2 mm, and a 45° notch was placed at the center of each specimen. An Izod Impact Tester (Resil impactor testing device) was used to conduct the impact energy test. A 1500 N hammer was launched at a 150° inclined angle while the specimen was firmly fastened in a vertical orientation (IZOD) on the machine's jaw. The tested specimen's impact energy (equation (1)) was carefully measured and documented, making it easier to use the appropriate equation to calculate the impact strength as indicated in equation (2), thus:

$$\text{Average Impact Energy} = \frac{1st+2nd+3rd}{3} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Impact Strength} = \frac{\text{Average Impact Energy}}{\text{Sample Thickness}} \quad (2)$$

Where,

Sample thickness = 3.2mm

2.3.2 Hardness test

The Micro Vicker Hardness Tester was used to conduct the hardness tests in line with ASTM D2240 specifications. On the mounting stage, a sample with exact measurements of 30 mm x 30 mm x 3.2 mm was placed. After that, the stage was elevated to make contact between the sample and the dial point and precisely apply the necessary force or pressure. The system screen immediately recorded the final hardness measurement.

2.3.3 Tensile test

The tensile strength test was performed on the Universal Testing Machine (model no. D-100KN, SN:190536) in accordance with the procedures outlined in ASTM D-638. For the examination, dumbbell-shaped samples with gauge measurements of 50 mm x 10 mm x 3.2 mm were meticulously manufactured. Each sample was subjected to a preset tensile force under carefully monitored circumstances. Essential tensile characteristics including tensile strength, percentage of elongation, and modulus were automatically calculated for each unique sample by utilizing the capabilities of the Universal Testing Machine.

2.3.4 Flexural test

The flexural strength test on the composite was rigorously carried out in accordance with the instructions provided in ASTM D-790. A specimen with exact measurements of 100 mm x 25 mm x 3.2 mm was positioned horizontally on a support span to create an 80 mm gauge length. A controlled three-point bending situation was generated by uniformly delivering a load to the specimen's center using a loading nose until the specimen failed. The highest load (measured in Newtons, N) and the accompanying deflection (measured in millimeters, mm) were obtained throughout the test. Equations (3) and (4) were then used to compute the flexural strength and flexural modulus of the examined composites respectively.

$$\text{Flexural Strength} = 3FL/2bd^2 \quad (\text{MPa}) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Flexural Modulus} = FL^3/4bd^3D \quad (\text{MPa}) \quad (4)$$

Where,

F = Maximum Load at break (N)

L = distance between the support spans at both edge of the specimen = 80mm

b = Sample width = 25mm

d = Sample thickness = 3.2 mm

2.4 Prediction of the mechanical behaviour of the examined composites

2.4.1 Artificial neural network (ANN)

The Artificial neural network was deployed to predict the flexural strength of the examined composites using multilayer perceptron (MLP) architecture. In this study, the dependent variable was the flexural strength while the independent variables included weight percent corn cob content, impact, hardness and tensile strengths. The partition was randomly assigned based on relative numbers of cases. The activation functions of the hidden and output layers were sigmoid and identity respectively with 2 hidden layers to obtain the networks as presented in Table 1 and shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 ANN networks for the prediction of the experimental flexural strength of the produced composites

Table 1. Prediction of flexural strengths of the produced composites by artificial neural network

Independent variables		Importance				
Hardness_of_Composite_HV		0.088				
Tensile_Strength_of_Composite_MPa		0.341				
Impact_Strength_of_Composite_I_per_mm		0.387				
weight_percent_CornCob		0.184				
Parameter Estimates						
Predictor	Predicted					
	Hidden Layer 1			Hidden Layer 2		Output Layer
	H(1:1)	H(1:2)	H(1:3)	H(2:1)	H(2:2)	Flexural_Strength_of_Composite_MPa
Input Layer	(Bias)	-0.192	-0.208	-0.445		
	Hardness_of_Composite_HV	0.490	-0.174	0.174		
	Tensile_Strength_of_Composite_MPa	-1.312	1.048	-0.200		
	Impact_Strength_of_Composite_I_per_mm	1.592	-0.988	0.252		
	weight_percent_CornCob	-0.952	0.303	-0.629		
Hidden Layer 1	(Bias)			2.02	0.477	
	H(1:1)			-2.570	-0.559	
	H(1:2)			1.866	-3.248	
	H(1:3)			-0.325	-0.456	
Hidden Layer 2	(Bias)					1.211
	H(2:1)					-2.882
	H(2:2)					0.088

Previous studies have utilized the technique to predict hardness and compressive strengths of composites (Ndukwe et al., 2024; Ndukwe et al., 2022), including corrosion rates (Ndukwe & Anyakwo, 2017c, 2017e, 2017d)

2.4.2 Multiple linear regression

In this study, the multiple linear regression was used to forecast the flexural strength of the produced composite considering the influence of wt.% filler, hardness, tensile and impact strengths. The obtained predictive equation takes the form, as presented in equation (5):

$$\text{Predicted Flexural Strength} = k_0 + p_1(\text{hardness}) + p_2(\text{tensile strength}) + p_3(\text{impact strength}) + p_4(\text{wt.\% corn cob in composite}) \quad (5)$$

Where,

k_0 = Intercept on flexural strength axis.

p_1 = Change in flexural strength for each 1 increment change in hardness

p_2 = Change in flexural strength for each 1 increment change in tensile strength

p_3 = Change in flexural strength for each 1 increment change in impact strength

p_4 = Change in flexural strength for each 1 increment change in wt.% corn cob content

2.4.3 Analysis of prediction inaccuracy

The degree of agreement between a predicted and actual value is determined using the mean squared error (MSE) and mean absolute error (MAE). The following formula provides the mean absolute error (Anyakwo & Ndukwe, 2017a):

$$\text{Mean Absolute Error (MAE)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n (d_i - e_i) \quad (6)$$

Where,

N = number of cases.

d_i is the predicted value.

e_i is the actual number.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterization of corn cob

3.1.1 FTIR result

The result of the FTIR test of corn cob filler is presented in Table 2, and shown in Figure 2. It produced unique spectral peaks at the following wavenumbers: 1513.3, 1602.8, 1733.2, 2903.6, and 3324.8 cm⁻¹. The peak at 1513.3 cm⁻¹ is indicative of a strong stretching vibration associated with nitro compounds (N-O). The existence of moderate bending vibrations associated with amines (N-H) is represented by the peak at 1602.8 cm⁻¹. Furthermore, the spectrum characteristics at 1733.2 and 2903.6 cm⁻¹ provide evidence of strong and moderate stretching vibrations belonging to aldehydes (C=O), saturated aliphatic molecules, and alkanes (C-H), respectively. Meanwhile, the

existence of C-H bonds derived from alkanes could be associated with hemicellulose breakdown processes (Anukam et al., 2017).

Fig. 2 FTIR result of corn cob

Table 2 Identified functional groups existing in corn cob

Wavenumber (cm-1)	Nature of vibration	Bond	Functional groups
1513.3 cm-1	Strong stretching	N – O	Nitro compounds
1602.8 cm-1	Medium bending	N – H	Amines
1733.2 m-1	Strong stretching	C=O	Aldehydes, and saturated aliphatic compounds
2903.6 cm-1	Medium stretching	C – H	Alkanes
3324.8 cm-1	Medium	O – H	Carboxylic acids
	Medium	N – H	10, 20 Amines, amides
	Strong	–C=C–H: C–H	Alkynes (terminal)
	Strong, broad	O–H, H–bonds	Alcohols, phenols

Furthermore, the signal at 3324.8 cm-1 indicates the presence of medium and broad stretching vibrations associated with carboxylic acids (O-H), 10,20-amines (N-H), amides, and alcohols/phenols with hydrogen bonding (O-H, H-bonded). It has been reported (Anukam et al., 2017) that the -OH group,

recognized as a major initiator, has been seen to accelerate condensation occurrences by stimulating dehydroxylation following the thermal breakdown of cellulose within maize cobs due to increased temperatures in the gasifier. These spectral properties give vital information about the composition and molecular structures of corn cob filler. Notably, the detection of essential functional groups, including the alcohol hydroxyl group, carbonyl group, phenolic hydroxyl group, and carboxyl group, supports the identification of lignin inside the corn cob (Huang et al., 2019). These identified elements serve as critical structural characteristics of the lignin component.

3.1.2 TGA result

Figure 3 displays the TGA curve that was discovered during investigation of the sample of maize cobs. The graph showed a weight loss that started off gradually at about 250 oC and then became more obvious between 400 oC and 600 oC. A total weight reduction of around 82.5% of the starting sample weight was seen.

Fig. 3 Result of thermogravimetric analysis of c fibre (corn cob)

The evaporation of moisture and volatile organic chemicals from the corn cob at lower temperatures is to blame for the first weight loss. Following this, there was a considerable weight loss between 400 and 600 oC, which is suggestive of the beginning of thermal degradation processes and the breakdown of the organic components inside the corn cob.

3.1.3 DTA result

The sample of corn cobs underwent multiple heat events during the DTA study. Indicating endothermic and exothermic processes, the measured DTA curve had different peaks and dips as shown in Figure 4. A sudden drop in the weight of the corn cob was observed at about 30 0C. At about 50 oC up to about 220 0C, the first endothermic event was noticed, denoting the evaporation of moisture from the sample. The second phase of endothermic reaction, which was pronounced, was observed from

220 to 400 OC, indicating a phase shift had taken place inside the sample. The breakdown of the hemicellulose found in maize cobs may be responsible for this change.

Fig. 4 Result of differential thermal analysis corn cob

Further increase in temperature between 400 and 600 OC indicated a significant exothermic reaction, reaching its peak at about 620 OC. This peak is associated with the breakdown of cellulose, a significant maize cob component. Between 620 and 880 OC, the derivative weight of the corn cob was observed to be relatively similar to the reference substance (α - alumina).

3.2 Effect of wt.% corn cob composition on the mechanical behaviour of the examined composites

The effects of wt.% corn cob compositions on the hardness, flexural, tensile, and impact strengths of the produced composites are presented in Table 3 and shown in Figures 5 and 6.

The addition of filler content resulted in a significant increase in hardness, reaching a high value of 53.13 Hv for the composite containing 8 wt.% filler. In comparison, the base composite of 100% LDPEw (control) had a minimum hardness of 46.87 Hv. Subsequent increases in filler content resulted in a small drop in hardness, which finally settled at 51.83 Hv.

Tensile strength analysis demonstrated a steady fall with the addition of filler, resulting in a reduction from the initial 50.92 MPa exhibited by the 100 % LDPEw (control) to 24.93 MPa with a filler composition of 2 wt.%, reflecting a reduction of slightly more than 50% in tensile strength. Nonetheless, when the filler percentage increased, the tensile strength gradually improved, peaking at 61.74 MPa for the composite containing 10 wt.% filler.

Table 3 Results of mechanical properties, experimental and predicted flexural values of the corn cob reinforced LDPEw composites

wt.% Corn Cob in Composite	Hardness (Hv)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Impact Strength (J/mm)	Flexural Modulus (MPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Predicted Flexural Strength by ANN		Predicted Flexural Strength by MLR	
						ANN (MPa)	Error in Prediction	MLR (MPa)	Error in Prediction
0	46.872	50.92	0.3712	603.149	32.61	32.609	0.001	32.622	-0.012
2	50.673	24.93	0.4343	721.64	35.35	35.671	-0.321	35.325	0.025
4	52.774	25.84	0.4015	769.408	35.94	35.552	0.388	36.227	-0.287
6	52.91	32.31	0.3079	750.063	33.6	33.670	-0.07	33.039	0.561
8	53.131	38.41	0.2211	642.553	29.69	29.759	-0.069	29.989	-0.299
10	51.834	61.74	0.1932	646.636	28.44	28.401	0.039	28.427	0.013

Fig. 5 Effect of addition of filler composition on the mechanical behaviour of the composite

Flexural strength increased gradually, peaking at 35.95 MPa when the filler composition was increased to 4 wt.% in the composite formulation. However, as the filler quantity was raised further, the flexural strength decreased. This pattern was replicated by the flexural modulus, as can be found in Table 2. The effect of the addition of corn cob filler on the impact strength of the composite is shown in Figure 6. Surprisingly, the composite composition with 2 wt.% filler attained the highest impact strength value of 0.4343 J/mm, demonstrating the favourable effect of filler content on the material's capacity to withstand strikes. Furthermore, as the content of the filler increased, the impact strength declined to as low as 0.1932

J/mm for the composite with 10 wt.% filler composition.

Fig. 6 Effect of the addition of corn cob filler on the impact strength of the composite

The analysis of the mechanical properties of the composite material in response to filler content highlights the delicate interplay between hardness, tensile strength, flexural strength, and impact strength. The findings highlight the possibility of modifying the mechanical properties of the composite material by selectively altering the filler content, providing useful insights for applications requiring specific mechanical qualities.

3.3 ANN and MLR Prediction of the experimental flexural strength of the produced composite

The prediction of flexural hardness strengths of the produced composites was achieved by utilizing artificial neural network and multiple regression. The predicted flexural strengths are presented in Table 2. In essence, the use of multiple linear regression led to the establishment of a predictive equation (i.e., equation (7)) as obtained from Table 4.

Table 4 MLR predictive equation’s coefficients and constant for the predicted experimental flexural strength

Predicted composite property	Constant	Model coefficients			
		Hardness of composite (Hv)	Tensile strength of composite (MPa)	Impact strength of composite (J/mm)	Corn cob in composite (wt.%)
Flexural strength	-62.718	1.669	0.137	27.660	-0.910

$$\text{Predicted Flexural Strength} = -62.718 + 1.669(\text{hardness}) + 0.137(\text{tensile strength}) + 27.66(\text{impact strength}) - 0.910(\text{wt.\% corn cob in composite}) \quad (7)$$

The impact strength had the most influence on the artificial neural network (ANN) model's prediction of the experimental flexural strength, accounting for 38.7% of the prediction accuracy. Tensile strength (34.1%), the weight percentage of maize cob reinforcement in the composite (18.4%), and hardness (8.8%) came next.

Table 5 Comparative analysis of the error in predicting the flexural strength of the produced composite using ANN and MLR

Error Measurement	Prediction of the experimental flexural strength by ANN	Prediction of the experimental flexural strength by MLR
Mean absolute error (MAE)	0.005333333	-0.000166667

The comparative analysis of the accuracy of the predicted value, as illustrated in Figure 7, was achieved using the mean absolute error method as expressed in equation (6), presented in Table 5, and shown in Figure 8. The results of the mean absolute error indicated that predictions obtained using MLR were closer to the experimental flexural strength values of the examined composites than those of ANN.

Fig. 7 Error comparison for the prediction of the experimental flexural strengths of the produced composites using ANN and MLR

Fig. 8 Comparative analysis of the error in predicting the flexural strength of the produced composite using ANN and MLR

In some situations, multiple linear regression (MLR) can predict the mechanical characteristics of composites more accurately than artificial neural networks (ANN). This precision frequently derives from MLR's efficacy with linear connections and its capacity to produce results that are easy to understand. In summary, research predicting the modulus of rupture and modulus of elasticity in particleboard demonstrate that MLR works effectively with structured datasets when the correlations between variables are linear (Tiryaki et al., 2017). Although MLR offers benefits, ANN is superior at identifying subtle, non-linear correlations and can surpass MLR in situations involving sizable datasets and complex variable interactions (Kim & Oh, 2021).

3.4 SEM Images of corn coB reinforced LDPEw composites

The SEM images of the produced composites are shown in Figure 9. The control sample with no reinforcement as shown in Figure 9(a), gave the least hardness value as well as flexural strength. The addition of the corn cob by 2 wt.% led to even dispersion of the filler across the matrix in Figure 9 (b). This was observed to improve the hardness, flexural, and impact strengths of the examined samples from 46.87 - 50.67 Hv, 32.61 – 35.35 MPa, and 0.3712 – 0.4343 J/mm respectively.

Fig. 9 SEM images of the produced composites: (a) 100wt.% LDPEw [control] (water sachet waste); (b) 2 wt.% fibre and 98 wt.% matrix; (c) 4 wt.% fibre and 96 wt.% matrix; (d) 6 wt.% fibre and 94 wt.% matrix; (e) 8 wt.% fibre and 92 wt.% matrix; (e) 10 wt.% fibre and 90 wt.% matrix

Further increment in hardness was achieved with the addition of 4 wt.% corn cob as a result of the even distribution of the filler within the LDPEw matrix (Figure 9 (c)). Directional reinforcements were observed in Figures 9 (d) and (e), when 6 and 8 wt.% reinforcements were blended with the matrix. This development decreased the impact strength from 0.3079 – 0.2211 J/mm while on the other hand increased the hardness to 53.13 Hv. The SEM image of the composite formulation with 10 wt.% corn cob revealed pointed clustering of the corn cob within the LDPEw matrix as shown in Figure 9 (f). This led to a peak in the tensile strength (61.74 MPa) but with slight reduction in hardness, flexural and impact strengths.

4 CONCLUSION

This research effectively combined mechanical testing, experimental characterisation, and predictive modeling to evaluate the potential of agricultural waste as a sustainable reinforcing ingredient in corn cob-reinforced LDPE waste composites. The research leads to the following conclusions:

1. The presence of essential functional groups, such as hydroxyl, carbonyl, and phenolic groups typical of lignin structure, was confirmed by FTIR analysis.

Thermal analysis (TGA/DTA) showed thermal stability up to 250°C, indicating that corn cob is thermally compatible with LDPE processing conditions.

2. The inclusion of maize cob filler resulted in ideal loadings for each property: impact strength peaked at 2 weight percent (0.4343 J/mm), flexural strength at 4 weight percent (35.94 MPa), and hardness peaked at 8 weight percent (53.13 Hv). At 10 weight percent (61.74 MPa), tensile strength showed a distinctive recovery pattern, first decreasing by 51% and then surpassing the initial matrix strength by 21.2%. As the filler amount increased, SEM examination showed a similar microstructural development from uniform dispersion to clustering.

3. In predicting flexural strength, multiple linear regression performed better than artificial neural networks (MAE = -0.000166667 vs 0.005333333), resulting in the following predictive equation: Predicted Flexural Strength = -62.718 + 1.669(hardness) + 0.137(tensile strength) + 27.66(impact strength) - 0.910(wt.% corn cob in composite).

5 REFERENCES

- Alichó, J., Mtunzi, F. F., Maia-Obi, L. P., Okoli, B. J., Qurix, B. W., & Modise, J. S. (2024). Effect of Surface Treatments on Zea mays Husk and the Behaviour of Husk/Low-Density Polyethylene Composites. *Sustainability*, 16(13), Article 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16135782>
- Anukam, A. I., Goso, B. P., Okoh, O. O., & Mamphweli, S. N. (2017). Studies on Characterization of Corn Cob for Application in a Gasification Process for Energy Production. *Journal of Chemistry*, 2017, e6478389. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/6478389>
- Anyakwo, C. N., & Ndukwe, A. I. (2017a). Mathematical model for corrosion inhibition of mild steel in hydrochloric acid by crushed leaves of *tridax procumbens* (asteraceae). *International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations*, 6(6), 81–89.
- Anyakwo, C. N., & Ndukwe, A. I. (2017b). Prognostic model for corrosion-inhibition of mild steel in hydrochloric acid by crushed leaves of *voacanga Africana*. *International Journal of Computational and Theoretical Chemistry*, 2(3), 31–42.
- Fayshal, M. A., Tasnuva Dhara, F., Mehedi Hasan, M., M Fairouz Adnan, H., & Mizan, T. (2023). Global plastic waste scenario: A review on production, fate and future prospects. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24225586.v1>
- Huang, J., Fu, S., & Gan, L. (Eds.). (2019). Chapter 2—Structure and Characteristics of Lignin. In *Lignin Chemistry and Applications* (pp. 25–50). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-813941-7.00002-3>
- Kim, Y., & Oh, H. (2021). Comparison between Multiple Regression Analysis, Polynomial Regression Analysis, and an Artificial Neural Network for Tensile Strength Prediction of BFRP and GFRP. *Materials*, 14(17), 4861. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14174861>
- Luo, Z., Li, P., Cai, D., Chen, Q., Qin, P., Tan, T., & Cao, H. (2017). Comparison of performances of corn fiber plastic composites made from different parts of corn stalk. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 95, 521–527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2016.11.005>
- Mishra, T., Mandal, P., Rout, A. K., & Sahoo, D. (2022). A state-of-the-art review on potential applications of natural fiber-reinforced polymer composite filled with inorganic nanoparticle. *Composites Part C: Open Access*, 9, 100298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcomc.2022.100298>
- Ndukwe, A., Azolibe, N., Okon, K., Christopher, P., Collins, M., Ozoh, C., Obasi, P., Eze, C., Ezem, A., Thomas, C., & Ogbodo, C. (2024). Prediction of hardness of palm inter-fruitlet membrane reinforced high-density polyethylene-waste (HDPEw) composites. *Acta Periodica Technologica*, 55, 27–46. <https://doi.org/10.2298/APT2455027N>
- Ndukwe, A. I., & Anyakwo, C. N. (2017a). Corrosion inhibition model for mild steel in sulphuric acid by crushed leaves of *clerodendrum splendens* (verbenaceae). *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Applied Science*, 3(3), 39–49.
- Ndukwe, A. I., & Anyakwo, C. N. (2017b). Modelling of corrosion inhibition of mild steel in hydrochloric acid by crushed leaves of *Sida acuta* (Malvaceae). *Int J Eng Sci*, 6(01), 22–33.
- Ndukwe, A. I., & Anyakwo, C. N. (2017c). Modelling of corrosion inhibition of mild steel in sulphuric acid by thoroughly crushed leaves of *voacanga Africana* (apocynaceae). *AJER*, 6(1), 344–356.
- Ndukwe, A. I., & Anyakwo, C. N. (2017d). Predictive Corrosion-Inhibition Model for Mild Steel in Sulphuric Acid (H₂SO₄) by Leaf-Pastes of *Sida Acuta* Plant. *Journal of Civil, Construction and Environmental Engineering*, 2(5), 123–133.
- Ndukwe, A. I., & Anyakwo, C. N. (2017e). Predictive model for corrosion inhibition of mild steel in HCl by crushed leaves of *clerodendrum splendens*. *IRJET*, 4(2), 679–688.

Ndukwe, A. I., Umoh, S., Ugwochi, C., Ogbuji, C., Ngolube, C., Aliegu, F., & Izuegbu, L. (2022). Prediction of compression strength of bamboo reinforced low-density polyethylene waste (LDPEw) composites. *Composites Theory and Practice*, R. 22, nr 3. <http://yadda.icm.edu.pl/yadda/element/bwmeta1.element.baztech-baeba140-67b8-4385-a19d-cf2201aabf0e>

Tiryaki, S., Aras, U., Kalaycıoğlu, H., Erişir, E., & Aydın, A. (2017). Predictive Models for Modulus of Rupture and Modulus of Elasticity of Particleboard Manufactured in Different Pressing Conditions. *High Temperature Materials and Processes*, 36(6), 623–634. <https://doi.org/10.1515/htmp-2015-0203>

Wong, D., Fabito, G., Debnath, S., Anwar, M., & Davies, I. J. (2024). A critical review: Recent developments of natural fiber/rubber reinforced polymer composites. *Cleaner Materials*, 13, 100261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clema.2024.100261>